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Implementation of the Principle of the Social Fairness in the Educational Process in Storozhishchensky Corrective Colony Shelter of the Smolensk Province in the Late 19th Century to the Early 20th Century

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of the educational process' organization in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in the Smolensk province, opened in 1894, through the implementation of the principle of social justice, reflected in the pedagogical ideas of the English reformer Robert Owen. It was found that in this institution for male juvenile offenders, the specified principle was used by applying adequate forms of education to them: labour, moral, mental and physical. The authors present the experience of the correctional colony shelter on re-education, correction and socialization of underage offenders, and the formation of their attitudes and values inherent in law-abiding citizens.

The methods and forms for achieving this were as follows activities of juvenile offenders in various types of household work: gardening, horticulture, beekeeping, handicrafts; military gymnastics, special exercises, outdoor games, walks; theoretical and practical teaching in agricultural schools, opened at the correctional institution; visits to the church, conversations, positive examples of teaching staff and their moralizing influence on children's personality.

Also the article considers methodological approaches, which were used by the teachers of Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter, such as natural science (biological), sociological, anthropological, cultural, educational, axiological and criminological.

Keywords: underage criminals, educational process, Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter, social fairness, methodological approaches, schools for young children, schools for workers' children.

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Introduction

The relevance of the problem raised in the article is explained by the fact that in the XXI century, just as in the pre-revolutionary period, the most important tasks are carried out in special institutions: education and development of juvenile offenders; implementation of measures aimed at their socialization in modern society.

In implementing these tasks, the pedagogical teams turn directly to the past experience of teachers, which even for now has not lost its importance in organizing the process of correcting underage offenders. Of specific importance in this situation is the principle of social justice, which is the key in the education of minors in conflict with the law.

Accordingly, it is important to analyse the theoretical approaches and applied methods used in the socialization process of this category of persons.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The goal of the research is on the basis of the materials of Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter of the Smolensk province in the late 19th - early 20th century to single out the specifics of the organisation of the educational process towards the underage law breakers in the context of the principle of the social fairness, reflected in the pedagogical views of Owen (Narskiy, 1971); to show upon which methodological approaches was the activity of the teaching staff towards the young criminals founded.

Literature review

At the current stage, the Russian Federation has a clearly structured legal and regulatory system protecting the rights of juvenile offenders and making the prevention of juvenile delinquency as one of its main goals. Legislation in this area consists not only of Russian laws, but also of international instruments. So, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the Declaration of the Rights of the Child adopted by the United Nations General Assembly (1959), the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), the World Declaration on the Survival, Protection and Development of Children (1990) contain articles and principles relating to the protection of the rights of the child, guarantees, obligations of gov-

ernment with regard to minors. The Russian Federation fully respects the positions reflected in these international documents.

In our country, there are laws relating specifically to this category of persons. Federal Law No. 120 of 24 June 1999 “On the Basics of the System for the Prevention of Child Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency” (with amendments and additions) specifies the main tasks and principles of activity for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency; the main directions of activity of authorities and institutions of the system for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency; proceedings on the placement of minors who are not criminally liable in special closed-type educational institutions. Article 2, paragraph 2, states that “the activities for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency are based on the principles of legality, democracy, humane treatment of minors, support of family and interaction with it, an individual approach to minors, respecting the confidentiality of information received, government support for the activities of local government authorities and public associations for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency, ensuring that officials and citizens are responsible for violations of the rights and legitimate interests of minors. (Federal Law “On the Basics of the System for the Prevention of Child Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency”, 1999).

The rights and interests of minors of all categories, including offenders, are also reflected in the Family Code, enacted on 29 December 1995, No. 223-FZ (hereinafter, as amended). Chapter 11 is devoted to the rights of minor children, for example, article 56 specifies the right of the child to protection (Family Code of the Russian Federation, 1995).

The Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, enacted on 13 June 1996, No. 63-FZ (hereinafter, as amended) contains articles relating to the criminal liability of minors, for example, section V, chapter 14, article 88 states the types of penalties prescribed to minors; article 90 specifies the use of coercive measures of educational influence (Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, 1996).

Federal Law No. 124-FZ of 24 July 1998 “On Basic Guarantees of the Rights of the Child in the Russian Federation” specifies the main directions for ensuring the rights of the child in the Russian Federation (Chapter II): Article 14.1 is about measures to promote the physical, intellectual, mental, spiritual and moral development of children; Article 15 is about protection of the rights of children in difficult life situations.

At present, there are quite a lot works devoted to the problem of education of underage offenders. The author Michael Gottfredson (2018) has analyzed a large amount of data from a number of countries, which

reveal the problem of crime. He stressed the importance of the environment directly influencing the child, as well as the importance of preventive measures. This author represents a criminological approach that considers the problem of juvenile delinquency. The researcher Murli Desai (2010) examined a preventive approach to psychosocial well-being in childhood; showed which measures are used to protect the rights of minors; and identified the importance of adoption and placement in foster families as a means of prevention. The author Albin Dearing (2017) raises the question of criminal justice based on respect for human dignity. He suggested that this could be achieved by changing the paradigm from criminal law that protected the public interest to criminal law that protected the rights of individuals. The author also argues that there is a need to change criminal justice that provides state rights to justice that gives offenders secondary rights. Mary Dillon (2017) presented new research findings on the impact of juvenile justice on adolescent development and life. The author describes how age affects the emergence of juvenile deviance; what measures should be taken to reduce the risks of crime. The researcher Frieder Dünkel (2016) showed which regulations provide juvenile justice and how they protect the child. He stressed that the children's rights movement more often leads to the full integration of legal safeguards in the juvenile justice process, avoiding adverse consequences for this category of persons. The author Geeta Chopra (2015) presents factors that lead children to conflict with the law. She described the concept and principles on which juvenile justice is based and showed the difference between restorative and punitive justice. She described the specificities of orphanages, children's homes and observation homes for children, who are in conflict with the law, and children in need of care and protection. The author presented options for non-institutional childcare (adoption, foster family). The researcher Nancy Marion (2011) is committed to the fact that working with minors who have committed serious crimes has traditionally been a public task. This is one of the areas where governments have consistently adopted laws to address the problem.

However, in order to expand the understanding of the specific features of the process of socialization of juvenile offenders in special institutions, it is necessary to refer to historical regional experience. This aspect is still relevant today in institutions for children in conflict with the law. Great interest in considering this problem represents the experience of Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in the Smolensk province (the end of the XIX century - the beginning of the XX century), which carried out education, correction and promoted socialization of juvenile offenders based on pedagogical ideas, namely, the principle of social justice of the famous English reformer Robert Owen (1771-1858).

Methodology

The problem of juvenile delinquency is particularly relevant at critical moments in society. It carries a lot of negative consequences, not only for the individual, but also for society as a whole. One such difficult

period in the history of the Russian Empire was the second half of the XIX century. The time of great state transformations, breaking the pre-existing social and political order, reforming all spheres of society – all these processes affected different groups of the Russian Empire in their own way. Minors have directly felt the impact of the great changes. It cannot be said that it was positive. During this historical period, the problem of juvenile delinquency became more acute in the country.

The personality of the underage offender was greatly influenced by the environment in which he grew up and was brought up (family, friends). Despite the importance of other factors (social and political structure, specific legislation in relation to this category of persons, etc.), it was the closest environment that had the primary influence on the formation of the minor's personality. Dril (1908) noted that in most cases a child committed a crime if there was an extreme need in the family. The situation became more complicated if the minor could not find a job. Often the father and mother were hardened against the "extra mouth", which affected their attitude towards the child and his personal qualities. To help the family or to escape from parental reproaches, such a minor often chose the criminal path as the only true way out of an extremely difficult situation, in his opinion.

Another factor that pushed children into crime was the low morality of their social environment, which gave minors a bad example. From an early age, a child who did not see a good attitude, love and care was formed as a morally unhealthy person. Lyublinskiy (1910) did not diminish the impact of the friends on the minor, whose assessment, views and opinions on certain issues were important to him. "Mostly, before children reach the age of understanding, they already have time to learn everything, to see everything and they will have nothing left of that holy innocence, which we so carefully protect in our children," - said the famous Russian criminologist of the second half of XIX - early XX centuries, Dril (1895).

In order to overcome this social problem, since the second half of the XIX century institutions for juvenile offenders have been opened in the Russian Empire. Children who had already committed a bad act were sent to such institutions. Accordingly, institutions for young offenders organized their work in such a way that after leaving them, the children did not embark again on the former vicious path, but became law-abiding citizens ready for independent living and achieving their goals in socially acceptable ways.

Precisely in this period of time the Smolensk province established the Smolensk society of correctional shelters and colonies for minors. Its goals were as follows: "to correct juvenile offenders, to have contempt for male juvenile offenders, both homeless and vagrants, and those whose parents are in prison, or the environment of their parents, relatives and guardians, due to the apparent viciousness or poverty of the parents, relatives and guardians under whose care they are, poses a danger to them to fall into vices and crimes" (Pavlovsky, 1894).

In order to achieve its goals, the Smolensk Society of Correctional Orphanage and Centre for Minors has begun to create handicraft children's homes and agricultural correctional centre, as well as similar institutions (correctional centre and orphanage).

As a result, in 1894, Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter was opened in the village of Storozhishchensk in the Smolensk province. It had the following objectives: "a) to educate male minors who were sent to the correctional centre by court verdicts; b) to have contempt for homeless and destitute male children who, under the influence of unfavourable conditions or the viciousness of their environment, are at risk of falling into vices" (Pavlovsky, 1894). Thus, it is worth paying attention to the fact that not only children who have committed an offence, but also minors at risk (street children and those in poverty) have been admitted to the correctional institution.

To achieve its goals, Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter set the following objectives: "a) full and complete development of pupils' personalities in moral and physical respect, b) obligatory literacy training of pupils and providing them with elementary information on general subjects, c) teaching pupils any profession (agricultural or handicraft)" (Pavlovsky, 1912).

It should be noted that the centre's teaching staff carried out the educational process for juvenile offenders based on the following methodological approaches: sociological, anthropological, natural science (biological), educational, axiological, cultural and criminological.

Table 1 presents the main ideas contained in these approaches, as well as their representatives. It should be noted that the names of some of them appear in several approaches simultaneously. This demonstrates the scientific continuity and complexity of the study of the problem of juvenile delinquency in the Russian Empire at the end of the XIX century – the beginning of the XX century.

Table 1. Content of Methodological Approaches to Reviewing the Specific Nature of Juvenile Offenders (Dumov, 2013; Dubonosova, 2008; Komarnitskiy, 2012; Ermolaeva, 2009)

Approach	Representatives	Main idea
Sociological	S.V. Poznyshev, N.S. Tagancev, A.I. Zak	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of negative processes taking place in all spheres of society. Underage offenders are regarded as victims of existing circumstances.

Anthropological	D.A. Dril, P.N. Tarnovskiy, N.A. Berdyaev, S.V. Poznyshev	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of hereditary factors supported by social aspects (homelessness, orphanhood, unlimited freedom). Underage offenders are regarded as victims of poor heredity and negative social situation.
Natural science (biological)	V.M. Bekhterev, I.M. Sechenov	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of disturbed physiological functions of the organism (e.g., CNS), “personal” disorders, adverse external and internal conditions. Underage offenders are regarded, on the one hand, as deserving justification for their own physiological defects (from the point of view of V.M. Bekhterev), but on the other hand, as people capable of being responsible for their actions (from the position of I.M. Sechenov).
Educational	K.D. Ushinskiy, P.G. Redkin	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of the lack of proper upbringing in the family, the existence of a bad attitude towards the child, different forms of violence against the child, etc. Underage offenders are considered as victims of the negative domestic situation, who have not received positive example and care from their parents.
Axiological	K.D. Ushinskiy	A minor (regardless of social status, decency or morality) is the highest value that requires a respectful humane attitude; a person with certain needs and individual interests.
Cultural	M.N. Gernet, N.N. Makovskiy, N.A. Okunev	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of the low culture of the social environment, the family and the immediate social environment of the minor, social ignorance and the lack of education of the general public. Children commit offences as a result of these factors, thus being victims of circumstances.

Criminological	A.M. Bogdanovskiy, A.F. Kistyakovskiy	Juvenile delinquency is a consequence of the parents' immoral character, lack of supervision and improperly formed social and moral attitudes. The measures taken to reduce juvenile delinquency should be preventive.
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In Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in the late XIX – early XX centuries, all these approaches were used in the organization of the educational process in relation to juvenile offenders. The institution's teachers considered pupils as victims of the circumstances that led to the crime: difficult social situation in the Russian Empire, in some cases, bad inheritance, physical and psychological defects, the low cultural level of the immediate environment (which also affected the culture of the juvenile himself), the negative and often devastating situation in the family, lack of care, violence that traumatized children's souls.

Of special interest in addressing this issue is the pedagogical concept of the English philosopher, teacher and social reformer Robert Owen. His views are interesting because they offer a solution to the problem of juvenile delinquency in Western Europe in the period from the end of the XVIII century to the beginning of the XIX century (which is expedient to extrapolate to the Russian Empire in the late XIX century - early XIX century).

It is worth noting that since the end of the XVIII century Western Europe began to “roll in” the industrial revolution, which led to the final victory of capitalist relations. This undoubtedly was a huge shock for society and caused a lot of social contradictions. If the bourgeoisie was not excited about this situation, but rather enriched in the conditions of machine production, the peasants and artisans found themselves in a rather difficult situation, due to their inability to adapt to such sharp social transformations. The workers, on the other hand, were subjected to harsh exploitation and had to live in harsh conditions.

Robert Owen was a direct witness to these events. He came from an artisan environment, and the caste was one of the victims of the industrial revolution in that historical period. Due to these circumstances, the boy left school at the age of 10 and was forced to start an independent working life. What he saw in England influenced the formation of his pedagogical views. So, Robert Owen was convinced that the social environment had a direct impact on the individual. He said that a person has never created and is not able to create his own character. This shows, in his opinion, that the individual is so powerless before the influence of society that he should not be responsible for his own actions and the consequences of his bad behavior. In this regard, attention should be paid to the words of Robert Owen that “the blame for the criminal nature

lays not on the individual, but on the system among which he was brought up. Destroy the circumstances conducive to the creation of criminal characters, and there will be no more crimes; replace them with circumstances designed to create habits to order, regularity, abstinence and work, and the individual will possess these qualities” (Narskiy, 1971).

Robert Owen can truly be called the great reformer of England in the late XVIII - early XIX century. The innovations he proposed and implemented were very necessary for Western Europe in such a difficult historical period. They made it possible to reduce juvenile delinquency, which was undoubtedly relevant abroad at that time because of the huge changes in all areas of society.

The English figure offered to start raising children from an early age. He was convinced that this required the opening of special institutions for the education and upbringing of all age groups. So in 1802 he opened a “School for Little Children”. The aim of the institution was not only to fully develop children’s personality, but also to protect them from the bad effects of the social environment. Thus, Robert Owen’s pedagogical ideas were preventive. The normal conditions of the environment in which the child was placed from an early age shaped a morally healthy personality, allowed the minor to develop adequate attitudes and instilled positive values. These conditions reduced the risk of the child committing offences. It should be noted that in the “School for Little Children” teachers tried to provide the children adequate physical education, which manifested itself in observance of the correct daily routine, healthy nutrition, healthy free time (outdoor) and gymnastics.

Aesthetic education was also particularly important in this institution. Children were taught to dance, to sing. This contributed to the development of dexterity, elegance.

Teachers tried to give pupils moral education, which was manifested in the development of “public spirit”. The personal positive example of teachers was particularly important for minors. The result was the acquisition by children of such excellent human qualities as honesty, decency, politeness, truthfulness, humanity, politeness towards other people (for example, helping friends in difficult times).

In the school for little children, pupils were also developed mentally. It was realized through conversations, during which children were introduced to the world around them. The conversations had a relaxed character and were interesting for children, effectively influenced their intellectual level.

The labour education of this contingent went through a game. This was due to the fact that, for little children, the game is a leading activity and it allows to learn new things faster and to consolidate the knowledge gained.

Robert Owen believed that people who are working with little children should not punish them. He assured that kindness, patience and affection are qualities that are especially necessary for a teacher to fulfil his professional duty. Robert Owen put them above education. For this reason, the teachers in the school for little children were a weaver and factory worker who did not have a high level of education, but had the above qualities.

Robert Owen's achievement is that in addition to a school for little children, he has opened a school for the children of workers. In this institution, the children were not only given ready-made knowledge, but also were taught to search for information independently, so that they could develop their cognitive abilities. The interior of the school contributed to the expansion of pupils' mental level: there were many exhibits; the walls were painted with images of plants and animals. Thus, the method of visibility was relevant for the education of children.

Physical education was realized through dancing lessons. Military gymnastics was introduced for boys, which not only positively influenced and strengthened the children's body, but also prepared them for military service.

The educational system at the school for the children of workers was built quite effectively. This is proved by the fact that there was a friendly atmosphere, no disagreements between children and teachers, respect for the personality of the other. Undoubtedly, labor education was of special importance here. The boys were taught different kinds of handicraft, work in the garden. Girls were taught knitting, sewing, cooking and cleaning.

It is worth noting that children from the age of five could attend this school. The humanity of Robert Owen is that he forbade the employment of children under the age of ten for factory work. It was in the time of the brutal exploitation of underage children and had a real social resonance. If the child went to the factory, he worked under a reduced regime until he was twelve years old. After a day at work, such children got the opportunity to study in the evening classes.

Robert Owen conducted his activities on the basis of the principle of social justice. It consists of a balance of rights and obligations of the individual, work and remuneration, crime and punishment (Rolz, 1995). The great reformer said: "Keep to your actions of justice, and you will soon gain the full and boundless trust of the lower classes. Apply in your treatment of them constantly and systematically the principle of kindness, and crimes, even those that infected the older generation, will gradually disappear, because even the worst tendencies, except in cases of incurable insanity, will not resist for a long time against the kindness shown decisively, systematically, cordially. Such behaviour, after a short practice, will prove to be the

most powerful and effective way to eradicate crimes and all harmful and bad habits” (Narskiy, 1971). This principle provided for equal treatment of teachers to pupils, the absence of exploitation (which was relevant for the countries of Western Europe in the late XVII - early XIX centuries), respect for children’s personality, the possibility for children to receive mental, labor, moral, aesthetic and physical education, regardless of belonging to a certain social class. It is reasonable to suppose that if, in England during this historical period, due attention had not been paid to the problem of exploitation of child labour, it would have entailed negative consequences. Thus, the risks of increasing the number of crimes committed by minors would increase. The measures taken by Robert Owen to support children of working families (through the opening of a school for little children, a school for the children of workers) have prevented the problem from spreading to a large extent. On the contrary, the creation of such schools allowed children to receive education, work skills and moral development, which had a positive impact on them and led to the widest possible personal development. The conditions created made it possible for children under 10 to be brought up in a normal environment and not to go to work with their parents in a factory (without basic education).

Thus, the principle of social justice was directly realized in the institutions opened by Robert Owen in England in the early XIX century. By following it, the situation in the country due to the industrial revolution was reduced and the risks of social vices were reduced.

It is worth paying attention to the fact that the events that took place in Western Europe during this historical period are similar in their features to the situation that arose in the Russian Empire in 60-70s of the XIX century. As noted above, in Russia at that time all spheres of society were being reformed. It was a time of great changes, abolition of serfdom, transformation of the former system of human relations in the Empire. Accordingly to this, there have emerged social classes which were unable to adapt quickly to such dramatic changes. Children were directly adversely affected by the reform costs. Under such conditions, it was impossible to get what they wanted, to meet the necessary needs, to show themselves from the good side. Therefore, for the Russian Empire since the second half of the XIX century, the problem of juvenile delinquency became urgent. In order to address this problem, the government decided to open special institutions for juvenile offenders (Pavlovsky, 1908-09).

In our opinion, the ideas of Robert Owen, materialized by him in the institute of formation of a new person, had a direct impact on the formation of educational and correctional system in institutions for juvenile offenders in the Russian Empire.

In Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in the Smolensk province, the pedagogical ideas of this person are reflected. The staff of the institution, as well as Robert Owen in his time, were of the opinion that the

minors had been brought to the path of crime by unfavourable difficult circumstances of life, the harmful impact of the social environment and the cost of education. The teachers believed that if the process of correcting wicked children was properly organized, they would become law-abiding citizens and would be able to live independently without violating social norms. This institution followed the principle of social justice, which was very necessary when dealing with children who were victims of a certain degree of injustice to ordinary people in the public system. This was reflected in the following features: Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter not only protected the children from bad influence (which was the goal of the school for little children and the school for the children of workers of Robert Owen), but also ensured a comprehensive personal development. The pedagogical staff of the correctional centre paid special attention to the rules: the pupils were often outdoors and their free time was useful (in summer the pupils took care of their own seedbeds and trees, which were rewarded for good behavior and good deeds) (Pavlovsky, 1903). As in the schools opened by Robert Owen, in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter the education of juvenile offenders was carried out in a multidimensional manner: physical, mental, moral and labour.

Physical education was provided with games and special exercises useful for the health of teenagers. Military gymnastics had special importance, which not only strengthened the pupils' organism, but also gave them positive personal qualities: discipline, responsibility, ability to interact with the team, attentiveness. It also prepared children for further military service, which was especially necessary for future defenders of the fatherland. It should be noted that there was a doctor in the colony who visited the institution several times a month to check the physical health of pupils. He was not directly involved in this kind of minors' education, but his presence in the correctional centre showed that the teaching staff was responsible for the children's health and paid attention to their well-being. In the case of illness, minors were free from all the activities in the correctional colony until their full recovery.

The mental development of juvenile offenders in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter was given special importance. For this category of children, it was extremely necessary, since the increase in their intellectual level contributed to positive personal transformations and to the change of criminal attitudes that had previously been formed by the dubious social environment into socially acceptable ones. In the institution pupils studied general subjects (reading, writing, counting, God's law) and special subjects (horticulture, gardening, beekeeping). Such subjects were related to the work of minors. In colony, teachers gave the children not only ready-made information, but also often put them in a situation where they had to find the material (mainly for practical classes) by themselves and present it to their fellows, having being prepared for a discussion on the topic. This certainly increased knowledge and intellectual potential for pupils. It should be added that at the correctional centre were opened schools that provided theoretical and practical training of pupils: Storozhishchensky Agricultural School of 1st class (opened in 1896),

Storozhishchensky Agricultural Low School of 1st class (opened on January 1, 1910), Storozhishchensky Practical School of Horticulture, Gardening and Beekeeping (opened in 1912). In these schools juvenile offenders received theoretical knowledge according to their level of intellectual development, which was supported by various kinds of work (agricultural, carpentry). The last were closely involved in labour education and directly reflected its objectives. The acquired practical skills allowed the pupils to learn a certain agricultural profession and to realize themselves further in this field, but already in independent life. (Pavlovsky, 1896; Pavlovsky, 1910; Pavlovsky, 1912). Many of the pupils had made significant progress in such work and were invited to neighbouring estates as workers at the end of the corrective period. This measure of intellectual and labour education not only reflected the principle of social justice (the right to education and decent work), but also had a preventive character: the risks of minors committing repeated offences in adult life outside the Smolensk colony were reduced. They were significantly socially protected from unemployment, the bad influence of former fellow criminals. Most importantly, the leavers of the institution began to realize that honest work can and should be lived, it will not lead to another violation of the law; former criminals are not excluded from society, but still remain members of the institution, capable of being necessary and useful for their country.

Labour education has undoubtedly contributed to the correction of juvenile delinquents. Thus, in the State Archives of Smolensk region were found materials indicating that in 1903, from 15 pupils leaving Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter 10 of them went to work in agriculture, 4 persons continued their education, 1 former pupil found himself in another profession (Pavlovsky, 1903).

The moral side of education in this institution for juvenile offenders was also given special attention by the teaching staff. The staff of the correctional colony influenced the moral side of the pupils with their own positive example. The teachers were aware that everything they said and did would not go unnoticed by the children. They were the example for the pupils and the children wanted to follow them. To achieve this, the teachers organized interaction with the juvenile offenders based on respect, trust and understanding.

It should be added that on the territory of Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter there was a church. The fact that the children visited it contributed undoubtedly to their religious and moral education.

The moral health of the pupils was guaranteed by applying adequate incentives to them. For example, for good behaviour and good deeds, children were rewarded with several hours or days of leave to their relatives (if they lived far from the correctional centre) and walks. Especially valuable for the pupils were packages with orders, assignment for responsible work and expression of trust. Juvenile offenders felt their own significance for the correctional centre as a whole and for teachers. This increased their self-confidence and

strengthened their desire to do good deeds. In addition to these encouragement measures, approval in the presence of the other children was actively used in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter.

It should be noted that the penalties used for juvenile offenders (reprimand, loss of trust, temporary isolation in a light punishment cell or a special room) did not deeply affect the honour and dignity of children. They were not insulted but the teachers clearly explained the reason of the punishment.

In these cases, the principle of social justice was directly implemented: for good deeds, children were rewarded, and for misconduct and breaking of the rules, adequate penalties were given to them.

Results

Thus, in the late XIX – early XX centuries, the educational process of juvenile offenders in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in the Smolensk province was based on a natural-scientific (biological), sociological, anthropological, culturological, educational, axiological and criminological approaches, which deeply reflected the nature of the problem of juvenile delinquency in the Russian Empire and made it possible to work effectively on the reeducation of these persons. Also, Robert Owen's pedagogical ideas, implemented by him in England in the early XIX century, were directly realized in this correctional centre during the difficult historical period. Robert Owen's understanding of the organization of interaction with the children of factory workers was humane (the child was the highest value and the schools described above were opened for his benefit) and it was based on the principle of social justice: children had the right to education and age-appropriate work; conditions were created for their comprehensive development.

Discussions

Robert Owen proposed and implemented a new concept of social interaction: not exploitation, but a human attitude to the lower classes of society.

The ideas of this person were transferred in Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter, despite the fact that they did not reflect the organization of education of juvenile offenders, but concerned another contingent (children of workers). However, they were preventive in nature and expressed ways of effectively achieving socialization in this category, which was the most important task of the correctional colony.

Conclusion

Summing up, we can say that Robert Owen's pedagogical ideas about social justice were directly used by the staff of Storozhishchensky corrective colony shelter in organizing educational work.

Labour, mental, moral and physical education, carried out on the basis of the principle of social justice, contributed to the preparation of pupils of this institution for adult life, formed them as law-abiding, decent citizens of the country.

Labour education was carried out through the participation of juvenile offenders in various types of household work in the institution: they were engaged in horticulture, beekeeping, handicrafts and garden work. Physical education was carried out through military gymnastics, special exercises, outdoor games and walks. Mental education of pupils was carried out through their theoretical and practical teaching in agricultural schools opened at the correctional centre. Moral education was carried out through visits to the church, talks, positive examples of teaching staff and their moral influence on the personality of juvenile offenders.

These types of educational impact combined to achieve a positive result: pupils were being corrected; their previous vicious attitudes changed; honesty and law-abiding became an important value for them.

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